

Rare type III responses: methods for code and simulation models (v1.0.0)

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Overview

This document supplements the publication “Empirical evidence of type III functional responses and why it remains rare” by (Kalinkat et al. 2023). We did some modeling exercises to show why knowledge of the functional response shape is crucial (see figure 1 in Kalinkat et al. 2023). We based our modeling approach on the models by Otto et al. (2007) for a three-species food chain and on Williams and Martinez (2004) for a 10-species food web. The R-Code for the models and the graphical output is available on Zenodo (Rall 2023, the code is also available at <https://github.com/b-c-r/rare-type-3-responses>).

Stability of a three-species food chain

The differential equation system

We based our modeling approach on an allometric food chain model (Otto et al. 2007). The model consists of a basal resource, B , an intermediate consumer, I , and a top consumer, T . The model is a set of differential equations in which the biomass densities are modeled:

$$\frac{dB}{dt} = B(1 - B) - \frac{F_{max_I} B^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + B^{q+1}} I \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = e \frac{F_{max_I} B^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + B^{q+1}} I - m_I I - \frac{F_{max_T} I^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + I^{q+1}} T \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = e \frac{F_{max_T} I^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + I^{q+1}} T - m_T T \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The basal biomass density, B , grows logistically with an intrinsic growth rate, r , of 1, and a carrying capacity, K , of 1 (Yodzis and Innes 1992, Otto et al. 2007). Therefore, these parameters do not appear in the model formulation above in Eq. 1. We will present all the following parameters as relative values to the unified basal growth rate and carrying capacity. Please read the original papers and references therein for an in-depth description and the model's rationale (Yodzis and Innes 1992, Otto et al. 2007).

The species interact by the *generalized* or *θ -sigmoid* functional response model (Real 1977) with F_{max} , being the maximum feeding rate (the asymptote), N_0 being the half saturation density, and q being the shaping exponent. Note that we used θ as shaping exponent in the main text, and θ relates to q as $\theta = q + 1$ (e.g., Williams and Martinez 2004, Rall et al. 2008, Vucic-Pestic et al. 2010). If $q = 0$, the functional response becomes the hyperbolic type II, and if $q > 0$, the functional response becomes the s-shaped type III (but see figure 1d in Kalinkat et al. 2023). The assimilation efficiency, e , controls how much energy is transferred to the next trophic level (ranging from 0 to 1), and how much is lost (e.g. by excreting feces). In addition to a biomass loss through consumption by a higher trophic level (see above), the intermediate consumer and the top consumer lose biomass by their metabolic rate, m .

The parameter values

We generally use the values used by Otto et al. (2007). Please read this publication for the biological rationale for using these values. The model is an allometric bioenergetic model (Yodzis and Innes 1992, Otto et al. 2007), meaning that nearly all parameter values can be calculated by body sizes, or the body size ratios (R , the relative body size relative to the body size of the basal resource). The metabolic rate for consumers can be calculated by:

$$m = a R^b \quad \text{Eq. 4.}$$

Here, a , is the allometric constant, and we set it to 0.2227 so that the resource species is an animal (Otto et al. 2007). The allometric slope, b , is set to -0.25, a common value often found in empirical studies (e.g., Peters 1983, Brown et al. 2004), and often used in modelling approaches (e.g., Williams and Martinez 2004, Otto et al. 2007, Rall et al. 2008).

The maximum feeding rate, F_{max} , also depends on allometry:

$$F_{max} = y m = y a R^b \quad \text{Eq. 5.}$$

Here, y is a multiplier calculating the maximum feeding rate based on the species' metabolic rate. We set the value to 8 (Otto et al. 2007), a biologically meaningful value (Yodzis and Innes 1992). The remaining values are $N_0 = 0.5$, $e = 0.85$, and we simulated a gradient of q ranging from 0 to 0.2 (1800 equally spaced values). We fixed the average body size ratio, R , to 100, a good approximation for predatory body size ratios (e.g., Brose et al. 2006, 2019).

Simulation engine and settings

We programmed the simulation model in **R** (R Core Team 2022). We used the package **odeintr** (Keitt, 2017) to simulate in **C++** via **R**. We simulated, as mentioned above, 1800 food chains across a gradient of 0 to 0.2, the shaping parameter q . We simulated each time series for 150,000 time steps. The initial step size of this adaptive simulation was set to 0.5. We compiled the **C++**-code using the function `compile_sys()` from **odeintr** (Keitt 2017). We adjusted the following arguments: `method = "rk54_a"`, `atol = 1e-8`, and `rtol = 1e-8`, to ensure a correct simulation in the chaotic states of the model. See the help files of **odeintr** (Keitt 2017) and references therein for more information. You can access the code on Zenodo (Rall 2023, the code is also available at <https://github.com/b-c-r/rare-type-3-responses>).

Analyses of the food chain simulations

We analyzed the last 5% of each time series and saved all extrema (i. e. all local minima and maxima) of each time series and each species. We deleted double entries to save disk space.

Diversity of a 10-species food web

The differential equation system

To show how the sigmoid responses affect biodiversity, we present a simulation of a 10-species food web based on the model by Williams and Martinez (2004). The model is an allometric bioenergetic model (Yodzis and Innes 1992, Williams and Martinez 2004, Otto et al. 2007, Rall et al. 2008). The equation system is as follows:

$$\frac{dX_0}{dt} = X_0 (1 - X_0) - \frac{0.5 y m_2 X_0^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_0^{q+1}} X_2 - \frac{0.5 y m_3 X_0^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_0^{q+1}} X_3 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\frac{dX_1}{dt} = X_1 (1 - X_1) - \frac{0.5 y m_2 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_2 - \frac{0.5 y m_3 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_3 - \frac{y m_4 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_4 \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\frac{dX_2}{dt} = \frac{0.5 y e m_2 X_0^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_0^{q+1}} X_2 + \frac{0.5 y e m_2 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_2 - m_2 X_2 - \frac{0.5 y m_5 X_2^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_2^{q+1}} X_5 - \frac{y m_6 X_2^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_2^{q+1}} X_6 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\frac{dX_3}{dt} = \frac{0.5 y e m_3 X_0^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_0^{q+1}} X_3 + \frac{0.5 y e m_3 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_3 - m_3 X_3 - \frac{0.5 y m_5 X_3^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_3^{q+1}} X_5 - \frac{0.4 y m_7 X_3^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_3^{q+1}} X_7 \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$\frac{dX_4}{dt} = \frac{y e m_4 X_1^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_1^{q+1}} X_4 - m_4 X_4 - \frac{0.4 y m_7 X_4^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_4^{q+1}} X_7 - \frac{0.8 y m_9 X_4^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_4^{q+1}} X_9 \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\frac{dX_5}{dt} = \frac{0.5 y e m_5 X_2^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_2^{q+1}} X_5 + \frac{0.5 y e m_5 X_3^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_3^{q+1}} X_5 - m_5 X_5 - \frac{0.2 y m_7 X_5^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_5^{q+1}} X_7 - \frac{0.2 y m_9 X_5^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_5^{q+1}} X_9 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$\frac{dX_6}{dt} = \frac{y e m_6 X_2^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_2^{q+1}} X_6 - m_6 X_6 \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$\frac{dX_7}{dt} = \frac{0.4 y e m_7 X_3^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_3^{q+1}} X_7 + \frac{0.4 y e m_7 X_4^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_4^{q+1}} X_7 + \frac{0.2 y e m_7 X_5^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_5^{q+1}} X_7 - m_7 X_7 - \frac{y m_8 X_7^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_7^{q+1}} X_8 \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$\frac{dX_8}{dt} = \frac{y e m_8 X_7^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_7^{q+1}} X_8 - m_8 X_8 \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$\frac{dX_9}{dt} = \frac{0.8 y e m_9 X_4^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_4^{q+1}} X_9 + \frac{0.2 y e m_9 X_5^{q+1}}{N_0^{q+1} + X_5^{q+1}} X_9 - m_9 X_9 \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

Here X_0 to X_9 stand for the biomass densities of the ten species. The food web has two basal resources (X_0 and X_1), and three top consumers (X_6 , X_8 , and X_9). The multi-species functional response splits the foraging effort spent across all species, and the total effort always sums up unity (e.g., McCann et al. 1998, Williams and Martinez 2004). We included those preferences, Ω_{ij} , directly as numbers into the equations above (e.g. X_9 uses 80% of his foraging time on X_4 and 20% on X_5). The rest of the parameters are as described [above](#).

The parameter values

Like the 3-species food chain model, the 10-species model is also allometric. In a food web model, the specific body size ratios, R , can be calculated according to the trophic level, L , and the average body size ratio in the food web, R_{av} (e.g., Rall et al. 2008):

$$R = R_{av}^{L-1} \quad \text{Eq. 16.}$$

We calculate the trophic level of species i by the sum of all weighed trophic levels of all resources j :

$$L_i = \sum \Omega_{ij} L_j \quad \text{Eq. 17.}$$

We calculated the metabolic rates, m_i , according to Eq. 4, with $\alpha = 0.2227$, and $b = -0.25$. The assimilation efficiency, e , is set to 0.85 as above. For the strong-interactions scenario, we set $y = 8$ and $N_0 = 0.5$, for the weak-interactions scenario, we set $y = 4$ and $N_0 = 1$. We sampled the body mass ratios randomly from a uniform distribution ranging from 10 to 100 for each species and each simulation run. Note that the two basal species always have a body mass ratio of 1. We simulated a q -gradient from 0 to 4 with 600 equally spaced steps.

Simulation engine and settings

As mentioned above, we programmed the simulation model in **R** (R Core Team 2022). We used the package **odeintr** (Keitt 2017) to simulate in **C++** via **R**. We compiled the **C++**-code using the function `compile_sys()` from **odeintr** (Keitt 2017). We adjusted the following arguments: `method = "rk54_a"`, `atol = 1e-12`, and `rtol = 1e-12`, to ensure a precise simulation in the chaotic states of the model. See the help files of **odeintr** (Keitt 2017) and references therein for more information. We initialized all ten species with randomly uniform assigned starting densities ranging from 0.1 to 1. We simulated the food web for 1000 time steps and checked if any species were below a biomass density threshold of 10^{-10} , if yes, this species counts as extinct, and we set the density to "0". We repeated this procedure 20 times, summing up to 20,000 timesteps. You can access the code on Zenodo (Rall 2023, the code is also available at <https://github.com/b-c-r/rare-type-3-responses>).

Analyses of the food-web simulations

We counted all remaining species at the end of each simulation. We analyzed the species richness using a GAM (Wood 2022). We used the according prediction function to create the prediction line, including the standard error lines (`se.fit = TRUE`). See the published code for details (Rall 2023 and <https://github.com/b-c-r/rare-type-3-responses>).

Software versions

We performed all simulations and analyses in **R version 4.2.2**, platform x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64 (64-bit) (R Core Team 2022) with the attached base packages: **parallel**, **stats**, **graphics**, **grDevices**, **utils**, **datasets**, **methods**, and **base**. We attached the following packages additionally: **mgcv 1.8-41** (Wood 2022), **nlme 3.1-160** (Pinheiro et al. 2022), **doParallel 1.0.17** (Daniel et al. 2022a), **iterators 1.0.14** (Daniel et al. 2022c), **foreach 1.5.2** (Daniel et al. 2022b), and **odeintr 1.7.1** (Keitt 2017). Other packages that were automatically loaded via namespace are: **compiler 4.2.2** (R Core Team 2022), **Matrix 1.5-1** (Bates et al. 2022), **tools 4.2.2** (R Core Team 2022), **Rcpp 1.0.9** (Eddelbuettel et al. 2022), **splines 4.2.2** (R Core Team 2022), **codetools 0.2-18** (Tierney 2020), **grid 4.2.2** (R Core Team 2022), **lattice 0.20-45** (Sarkar 2021).

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